

Generative design of RHS/SHS profiles using Conditional Variational Autoencoder (CVAE)

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ABSTRACT

Conditional Variational Autoencoder are used throughout the literature in the sense of a performance-based generative design. The main advantage is the possibility of an inverse problem formulation, allowing the exploration of design possibilities on a pareto-front. The presented paper is based on a novel approach to carry out a beam-element analysis that accounts for the nonlinear deformation behaviour of various RHS and SHS sections, made from mild and high-strength steel, denoted as “deep neural network direct stiffness method” (DNN-DSM). Up to now, predictions within this method were made on the basis of deep neural networks (DNN) in a feed forward procedure. Those predictions are made by trained DNN models resulting from an extensive pool of geometrically material nonlinear simulations with additional imperfections (GMNIA) using shell based models. First implementations of this method are able to accurately predict the nonlinear load-displacement and moment-rotation behavior, as well as the corresponding load bearing capacity of various sections with great accuracy. The extension to conditional variational autoencoder allows a more dynamic design, including performance and code based parameters as a preselection criterion for the overall design.

Keywords: CVAE, local buckling, high strength steel, machine learning

1 INTRODUCTION

Fig. 1. Prediction of the cross-section capacity for hot-rolled steel sections taking into account strain-hardening a) RHS profiles; b) SHS profiles

This paper follows up on investigations on a data driven deep learning approach introduced in (1,2), presenting the idea of using deep neural networks (DNN) as surrogates in the direct stiffness method (DSM) to predict the nonlinear stiffness matrix of a beam element under different deformations and rotations acting in plane. The developed deep neural network (DNN) models were trained on data sets derived from a pool of numerical (LBA and GMNIA) shell FE simulations, designed in such a way that only local buckling is the main instability phenomena for the investigated rectangular and squared (RHS and SHS) cross-sections. This paper uses data sets, which were collected to make prediction on the simulated load bearing capacity of individual hot-rolled and cold-formed RHS/SHS cross-sections (here only for compression) to make first investigations how deep learning, in particular the architecture of conditional variational autoencoders (CVAE) can be used to explore the design space based on preselected conditions (performance criterions) in an inverse solution attempt. The first part of the paper (Section 2) introduces the overall assumptions made to create the FE models. It further explains the step of data development and extraction to create the data sets used herein. This part was presented throughout several publications and covers only the most necessary information. Sections 3 is used to describe predictions made by a DNN in a feed forward sense, meaning that features are used to make a forward prediction of the local buckling reduction factor χ of individual cross sections. A representation of such a forward prediction is shown in Fig. 1 for hot-rolled RHS/SHS profiles. Section 4 will describe the idea of using a CVAE in member design, it explains the model architecture and shows first results made by the network.

2 FE MODEL ASSUMPTIONS AND DATA DEVELOPMENT

2.1 FE Model verification and validation

This section provides necessary background information on FEM modelling decisions, made to create the used data-sets in Section 2.2. However, the main verification work against experimental test goes back on the Hollosstab project (<https://www.steelconstruct.com/eu-projects/hollosstab/>), which was presented throughout many publications (3–5) and subsequently rooted in the GSRM method (generalized slenderness based resistance method) (6,7). Note, all corresponding test results and Abaqus simulations for SHS and RHS sections were collected and can be downloaded from (8). The presented FE-models were partially adapted based on this investigations and were further developed in(2) to match the conditions for local buckling phenomena exclusively. The developed FEM models are described as follows:

- *Use of isoparametric shell elements of type S4R, with a mesh density of around 60 elements in circumferential and 50 – 100 elements per meter in longitudinal direction.*
- *Geometry based on code provisions of (EN 10210-2:2006 (9), EN 10219-2:2006 (10)) with a local length L (longitudinal direction) set as the bigger value of either the width W or the height H of the cross-section.*
- *The loads and deformations are applied through defined reference points (RF-Points) which are located at the upper and lower edge of the cross-section, connected through multiple point constraints (MPC-Pin formulation) to associated node sets along the upper and lower profile outer edge.*
- *Non-linear material models for hot-rolled (bilinear + non-linear model) and cold-formed steel (two-stage Ramberg Osgood model) implemented according to Yun and Gardner (11). Residual stresses were not explicitly considered.*
- *An LBA (linear buckling analysis) analysis is carried out in order to identify the elastic critical buckling resistance of the cross-section and the eigenshape as the critical imperfection form, derived from the load case of centric compression.*
- *A GMNIA (geometrically and materially nonlinear analysis with imperfections) simulation is performed to determine the realistic buckling resistance that considers both material and geometric nonlinearities. Abaqus calculations were performed using the static general stress analysis.*

2.2 Data development

Table 1. Used profiles and parameters

Used Profiles	Number of Sections	Dimension Range c/t
SHS hot-rolled	106	8.0 – 47.62
SHS cold-formed	142	8.0 – 47.62
RHS hot-rolled	113	9.52 – 56.25
RHS cold-formed	165	12.5 – 55.55
Used Parameters	Number of Parameters	Values
Steel grade f_y	3	S355, S460, S700/S690
Material model (hot-rolled)	1	Bilinear + non-linear hardening model
Material model (cold-formed)	1	Two Stage Ramberg Osgood
Imperfection amplitude e_0	3	B/200, B/300, B/400
Abaqus simulations		
LBA Compression		526
GMNIA Compression		4734

The used data sets are based on the results from Abaqus LBA and GMNIA simulation. 526 European hot rolled and cold-formed RHS and SHS profiles, three different steel grades ranging from mild to high-strength (S355, S460 and S700), as well as three different local imperfection amplitudes (B/200, B/300 and B/400; where B is the smaller dimension of either the profile height or width (12) were taken into account. In sum, 4734 GMNIA simulation were run to create the basis for data extraction. Subsequently, the information from simulations was collected and stored in .csv files. The LBA simulations were used to provides the critical elastic buckling load F_{cr} , the GMNIA simulations on the other hand the load-deformation curves and the maximum reached loads F_{max} . Note, results from the load deformation curves were not used herein and are therefore not part of the data sets. Furthermore, the data sets were completed with geometrical and material parameters in order to better describe individual parameters. A corresponding data set example is provided by a d-dimensional (Euclidean) vector in Tab. 2.

Table 2. Sample of the extracted data set

H mm	W mm	t mm	L mm	A cm ²	I_y cm ⁴	$W_{y,el}$ cm ³	$W_{y,pl}$ cm ³	e mm	f_y N/mm ²	K_e N/mm	F_{max} N	F_{cr} N
250	150	12.5	250	92.1	7387	591	740	0.5	355	7736400	3691100	23493000
200	100	8	200	44.8	2234	223	282	0.5	690	4704000	3065900	7508420
200	100	16	200	83	3678	368	491	0.25	460	8715000	4586900	60234500

3 FORWARD PREDICTION

3.1 Concept of Neural Networks

The idea of neural networks goes back on investigations from the 1940s by McCulloch and Pitts (13), being further developed by D. Hebb (14) and M. Minsky and S. Papert (15) in their research. Having its roots in the logical description of the transmission of impulses between individual neurons within a larger nervous system, deep learning method are further developed and nowadays widely used throughout different domains in architecture, engineering and construction. This increasing popularity is fuelled by the access to a large amounts of data, the availability of graphics processing units (GPUs), the development of algorithms, and easier access to the machine learning field - than decades ago - through the development of high-level libraries/APIs.

$$y(x) = a \cdot \left(\left(\sum W_n \cdot x_n \right) + b \right) \quad (1)$$

An artificial neuron consists of three main components, the weights, the bias and an activation function and is usually represented as shown through Eq. (1). The input parameters (features) are multiplied with randomly initialized weights, which are updated over a certain number of epochs during the training of the DNN model and are an indicator of the strength of a connection within a network. Parameters which do not affect the overall prediction are set over the training period to small values. The bias is an additional trainable value (zero or non-zero) which is added to the summation of the weighted inputs in a neuron. The neuron is mathematically represented through a single vector, which is passed to an activation function with an inherent predefined threshold. This concept can be further expanded to a more complex systems with more neurons and layers to increase the amount of trainable parameters for more non-linear problems, see Fig. 2 b).

Fig. 2. a) Single layer perceptron; b) multi-layer perceptron

At the end of each network prediction a loss function is used to measure the deviation between the real and the predicted value. In terms of regression problems two very common representations for the error metrics are used as loss definitions, i.e. the mean squared error and the mean absolute error, see Eq. (2) and (3).

$$MSE: L = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\delta_i)^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$MAE: L = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\delta_i| = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (3)$$

Based on the loss definition, weights and biases are updated through gradient descent and backpropagation of the network, meaning that the derivative of every node is taken by using the chain rule and applied gradient descent method, see Eq. (4) and (5).

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial v} \cdot \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \quad (4)$$

$$x^{(j+1)} = x^{(j)} - \eta \cdot \nabla f(x^{(j)}) \quad (5)$$

3.2 DNN Architecture and Hyperparameters

The DNN architecture, corresponding hyperparameter tuning, as well as feature engineering was part of previous investigations, summarized in several publications (1,16,17). The reader is referred to those for detailed information. A combination of random and grid search parameter exploration was

conducted in order to detect overall tendencies, leading to the parameters presented in Tab. 3. The network optimization was performed on the basis of a train and test philosophy, meaning that a specific data amount was used for the training (80%) and an additional independent amount for the validation process (20%).

Table 3. DNN architecture and used hyperparameters

Model Parameters	Selection
Hidden layer 1	27
Hidden layer 2	27
Hidden layer 3	18
Hidden layer 4	9
Activation function	ReLU
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.0005
Epochs	6000
Batch size	128

3.3 Selected results

The overall prediction accuracy was in all cases very high, with an averaged r^2 value of 0.99 resulting from the data sets used for training and testing of the DNN models, meaning the comparison between the predicted cross-section resistances and the GMNIA simulations as the true values. Tab. 4 summarizes some of the statistical outputs from the trained models. Thus, the 95% confidence describes the level of certainty within a calculated prediction interval of 95%. Here the calculated interval values are close between 1.00, which would indicate a perfect result.

Further, a comparison was done to match the representation of the resistance curves from EN 1993-1-5 (s. Fig. 1). A normalized representation format for buckling was chosen, where the x-axis is the relative local slenderness $\bar{\lambda}$ and the y-axis the buckling knock down factor χ . Simulations and predictions were plotted on top of each other to showcase the achieved accuracy. In regions, where the cross-section would be classified as class 1 or 2, strain hardening is clearly visible while showing its positive effects in a much higher load bearing capacity compared to EN 1993-1-5. In more slender regions the cross-section capacity follows the buckling curves.

The three different steel grades for hot-rolled and cold-formed steel are clearly visible in the capacity prediction in a separation into three branches. The higher branch is addressed to the steel grade of S355 and the lower branch to S690/S700. This makes sense, since the strain hardening ratio decreases for high strength steel compared to mild steel. Beyond the plateau, no clear separation between steel grades and imperfection amplitudes is visible and the branches fall into one overall capacity prediction.

Table 4. DNN model accuracy evaluation

Profiles	μ	σ^2	cv	95% confidence
SHS hot-rolled and cold-formed	1.00	1.24e-5	0.003	0.999-1.000
RHS hot-rolled and cold-formed	1.00	9.26e-6	0.003	1.000-1.001

A more evident accuracy comparison can be drawn from Fig. 3. Fig.3 a) and c) show a summarized representation for all hot-rolled and cold-formed SHS and RHS profiles. The x-axis displays the relative local slenderness, the y-axis a direct comparison between the predicted results and the target values (non-linear Abaqus GMNIA simulations) resulting in a normalized manner. The deviations for compression are in some individual cases around 2%, in all other cases below. Additional frequency plots explain the distribution of the predictions according to their error, see Fig 3 b) and d).

Fig. 3. Comparison between DNN model predictions and GMNIA simulations as the ground truth a) hot-rolled and cold-formed SHS profiles; b) hot-rolled and cold-formed RHS profiles

To conclude this evaluation a final remark is made towards the enormous time advantages. Each profile series (106 SHS hot-rolled profiles, 142 RHS hot-rolled profiles, 113 SHS cold-formed profiles, 165 RHS cold-formed profiles) has three parameters for the steel grade and the local imperfection amplitude. The DNN model prediction takes around 4 to 6 second to predict all values of each listed profile. Note, this procedure does not involve the DNN-DSM algorithm and is only based on the tensorflow implementation. This is far beyond the calculation velocity recorded for the Abaqus calculations. Neglecting the modelling time, always two calculations need to be performed: LBA and GMNIA. The LBA takes around 5 to 10 seconds to estimate the first eigenmodes. The GMNIA around 20 to 40 seconds for each profile. To be fair, the DNN model used herein only predicts a discrete point (maximum force or moment) on the load-deformation/moment-rotation curve and not the whole course.

4 INVERSE PREDICTION

4.1 General idea

Generative design has become a major application domain throughout the last years, especially in highly prominent and widely accessible fields for the general public, such as computer vision or

language interpretation. Generative design on the other hand is mostly unexplored in the civil engineering domain, due to different shortcomings connected to data-scarcity, -scatter and -accessibility. However, as presented in Section 2 and 3, a data based simulation approach is highly suitable in the design of steel structures under the condition of well validated FE models. In contrast to a feed forward prediction, as done in Section 3, a conditional variational autoencoder allows to explore the design space and make inverse predictions based pre-set performance conditions, providing the engineer an intuitive tool. Examples can be drawn from (18) or (19), for the design of vertical gardens or pedestrian bridges. A similar approach by using a classical CVAE is chosen within this paper in the framework of a preliminary investigation on design space exploration, associated possibilities and advantages compared to feed forward predictions.

4.2 Model description and results

Fig. 4. a) CVAE model architecture; b) latent space representation for dimension $z[0]$ and $z[1]$; c) latent space representation for dimensions $z[0]$ and $z[1]$

The architecture of the chosen CVAE is shown in Fig. 4 a). The architecture of the encoder matches the one of the DNN model from Section 3. Further, this architecture is inverted and used for the decoder. The condition y is fed to the encoder together with the set of features x , predicting the mean and the standard deviation and the latent vector. The decoder used the information from the latent

vector z , as well as the pre-set condition y to predict \hat{x} . Each block in the encoder and the decoder is comprised of a fully-connected layer with a ReLU activation function. The latent representation was chosen to have 4 dimensions, meaning that μ , σ and z are represented each through 4 vectors. Once the model is trained, the decoder generates new samples \hat{x} based on a specific performance metrics y . The DNN models from Section 3 are used to compute the mapping from \hat{x} to an approximate performance metric \hat{y} . It acts as a reliability estimator for generated designs and allows to validate the reconstruction error between the a requested condition y and the predicted performance of the generated design \hat{y} . Tab. 5 shows summarizes the input features and the conditioned performance criterion, here in a preliminary step exclusively the load bearing capacity of a cross-section.

Table 5. CVAE used features and conditions

	Features x	Condition y
SHS hot-rolled and cold-formed	$H, t, A, I_y, W_{el}, W_{pl}, e, f_y, F_{cr}$	F_{max}
RHS hot-rolled and cold-formed	$H, W, A, t, I_y, W_{el}, W_{pl}, e, f_y, F_{cr}$	F_{max}

Tab.5 summarizes the used input features and the conditioned performance criterion. A first output from the trained model can be drawn from the latent representation in Fig. 4 b) and c), representing the learned mean values μ . A clear data separation can be detected from the output, where individual areas are formed represented by a denser cluster formation.

Using the steel grade f_y for labelling links the data points to the parameters S690, S460 or S355, leading to an even clearer results. This result shows that the data set can be separated in its latent representation and thus explained based on parameters. Certain areas can now be assigned to a steel grade, which provides an inherent filter for data generation, further giving the possibility to navigate through the design space.

Fig. 5. Model verification based on a different condition range a) sampled predictions for $\chi = 1.0$; b) sampled predictions for $\chi = [0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0, 1.1, 1.2]$

The advantage given by a CVAE is the possibility to sample/generate new data from the latent representation based on a specific condition. Fig. 5 shows outputs generated from a different condition range, i.e. different values for the buckling knock down factor χ . The generated data range \hat{x} is taken as an input for a feed forward prediction by a pre trained DNN model from Section 3. Fig. 5 a) shows the predicted results done for the buckling reduction factor of $\chi = 1.0$, meaning that the sampled profiles should reach the plastic capacity located around the plastic plateau. The comparison

shows a high achieved accuracy with an $r^2 = 0.998$ for the sampled data. In an additional step a range for the buckling reduction factor from $\chi = 0.7 - 1.2$ was chosen to produce samples from the entire slenderness range. Here, the overall prediction precision drops to an $r^2 = 0.956$, with a pronounced scatter in the range around $\chi = 0.7 - 0.8$, connected to higher slenderness values beyond the plastic plateau. This may be addressed to the fact that there are generally fewer data points in this area due to the used profile dimensions based on European standards. Normally, the profile series are designed in such a way that local buckling is not the driving design criterion, pushing the reached local slenderness towards lower values.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In both cases, the forward and the inverse prediction showed promising results. The presented forward prediction was introduced in sever publications, where a great effort was set on feature engineering, DNN model exploration (hyperparameter tuning) and the integration into a novel method (DNN-DSM (2)). However, from the very general design perspective not every parameter is known from the beginning and is strongly based on an engineering intuition, raising the demand for an explainable “co-pilot” application/model for conceptual design. The last part of this paper is dedicated to this idea, whereby very promising results have already been obtained in initial investigations, both in terms of explainability and prediction accuracy.

Nevertheless, sever open points need to be addressed in the course of ongoing investigations:

- *Detailed investigations on hyperparameter tuning are under way, since the used model architecture is a first attempt to obtain reasonable results.*
- *A more refined latent space exploration in order to explain the learned pattern more precisely. This enables the possibility to steer through the design space*
- *Applying the CVAE model to the data sets for hot-rolled and cold-formed RHS and SHS profiles, since the presented investigations in Section 4 only considered the data set for hot-rolled RHS. Further, a gradual combination of the data sets is being planned to enable a more general design consideration.*

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